

COURSE STRATEGY AS PERCEIVED BY B.ED STUDENTS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION MODE

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Abstract:

Distance education is a mode of education that focuses on teaching methods and technology with the aim of delivery of teaching often as an individual basis to the students who are not physically present in a traditional educational setting which is a classroom. It has been described as "a process to create and provide access to learning when the source of information and the learners are separated by time and distance or both". It is an opportunity to learn at the own pace, place and convenience of the learner. The present study reports on the perception of students learning through distance education on Course Strategy. The Scale on Course Strategy developed and standardized by Karuppasamy, M & Muthumanickam, A. (2014) was adopted for the present study. The result indicates that perception towards Course Strategy among B.Ed. students is satisfactory and some of the independent variables exert a significant influence on the same.

Key Words: Perception of Course Strategy, B.Ed. Students.

Need for the Study:

The developing countries like India have been facing problems in providing education to all through formal education system. In our country, we have number of colleges which is not sufficient to provide an opportunity to all the students to learn higher studies. Distance Education mode is only an alternative one. Distance education is a mode of education that focuses on teaching methods and technology with the aim of delivery of teaching often as an individual basis to the students who are not physically present in a traditional educational setting such as classroom. It has been described as "a process to create and provide access to learning when the source of information and the learners are separated by time and distance or both". It is an opportunity for the learners to learn at their own pace, place and convenience.

It is noteworthy that the universities offer teacher education programme (B.Ed. course) as a gift to the teachers in In- service. The teacher education programme in distance education mode is different from the other programmes in the sense that it trains the student teacher for a profession. It has different objectives, methodology, content and the expectation when compared to the other courses.

The students of distance education have minimum required number of face to face contact classes. Here Course Strategy has been planned to conduct the B.Ed course an also execution by the University. Hence the investigators thought of studying the perception of B.Ed. distance education mode students on Course Strategy.

Terms and Definitions:

- Course Strategy** : Refers to course design and execution by the distance education institution.
- Perceived** : refers to the ability of understanding about student support services through distance education mode
- B.Ed. Students** : refers to the candidates those who are studying B.Ed. course through distance education mode of different universities in Tamil Nadu viz., Annamalai, Bharathidasan, Madurai Kamaraj and Manonmaniam Sundaranar Universities

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variable:

Perception on Course Strategy

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male / Female
- Age : Upto 29 / 30 and Above
- Educational Qualification : UG degree / PG degree
- Teaching Experience : Upto 10 years / 11 years and above
- Optional : Arts group / Science group
- Medium of Instruction : Tamil / English
- Family Climate : Congenial / Disturbed

- Study Habit : Individual / Group
- Locality : Rural / Urban
- Newspaper Reading : Regularly / Rarely
- Mode of Study at Degree level : Regular / Distance mode
- Viewing Educational T.V Programme : Regularly / Rarely
- Listening Educational Radio Programme : Regularly / Rarely

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the level of perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in the level of perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode in terms of select social variables.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- B.Ed. students in distance education mode have average level of perception on Course Strategy.
- Select social variables exert a significant influence on perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode.

Methodology – In – Brief:

- Design : Descriptive
- Method : Normative
- Technique : Survey

Sample:

A sample consists of 1850 B.Ed. students studying through distance education mode in Annamalai, Bharathidasan, Madurai Kamaraj and Manonmaniam Sundaranar Universities was constituted.

Tools Used:

The following tools were constructed and standardized by Karupphasamy, M., and Muthumanickam, A., (2014) was used in the present study.

- Perception Scale on Course Strategy ()
- General Information Sheet

Statistical Treatment:

- “t” test between the large independent samples.
- Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation

Hypotheses Verification:

Hypothesis 1: B.Ed. students in distance education mode have above the average level of perception on Course Strategy.

The empirical average score of perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode involved in this study is found to be 60.94, while the theoretical average is 35 only. Thus the perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode is found to be more than average level.

Hence the hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Differential Studies on Perception on Course Strategy:

Perception on Course Strategy and Independent Variables

Hypothesis 2: Select social variables exert a significant influence on perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode.

The details of results of test of significant difference between the mean scores of perception on Course Strategy in terms of Independent variables are given in table 1.

Table 1: Significance of Difference Between the Means of Perception on Course Strategy: Independent Variables – Wise

Variable	Sub-variables	N	M	SD	‘t’ - value	Significance At 0.05 level
Gender	Male	290	59.717	10.874	2.181	Significant
	Female	1560	61.169	7.496		
Age	Upto 29	184	59.385	9.082	2.477	Significant
	30 and above	1666	61.114	8.005		
Educational qualification	UG degree	1039	61.832	7.321	1.997	Significant
	PG degree	811	60.269	9.058		
Teaching experience	Upto 10 years	645	60.037	9.024	3.32	Significant
	11 and above years	1205	61.426	7.572		
Optional subject	Arts group	1613	61.141	7.964	2.501	Significant
	Science group	237	59.581	9.072		
Medium of	Tamil	1285	61.509	7.935		Significant

instruction	English	565	59.620	8.453	4.497	
Family climate	Congenial	1651	61.347	7.612	4.327	Significant
	Disturbed	199	57.914	10.873		
Study habit	Individual	1555	60.901	8.189	0.507	Not Significant
	Group	295	61.155	7.836		
Locality	Rural	1153	61.183	7.948	1.890	Not Significant
	Urban	697	60.512	8.433		
Newspaper Reading	Regularly	1321	61.329	8.112	3.244	Significant
	Rarely	529	59.975	8.110		
Mode of study at Degree level	Regular	296	57.907	9.956	6.078	Significant
	Distance mode	1554	61.694	7.295		
Viewing educational T.V. programme	Regularly	542	60.909	7.700	0.134	Not Significant
	Rarely	1308	60.958	8.308		
Listening educational Radio programme	Regularly	542	61.866	7.946	2.127	Significant
	Rarely	1308	60.773	8.157		

It is evident from the above table; out of thirteen variables Ten variables exert a significant influence on perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance education mode. Hence Hypothesis 2 is partially accepted.

Conclusions:

The specific conclusions emerge out the present investigations are as follows:

- B.Ed. students in distance education mode have above the average level of perception on Student Course Strategy.
- Perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance mode is dependent on
 - Gender
 - Age
 - Educational qualification
 - Years of teaching experience
 - Optional subject
 - Medium of Instruction
 - Family climate
 - Newspaper reading
 - Mode of study at degree level
 - Listening educational radio programme
- Perception on Course Strategy among B.Ed. students in distance mode is independent on
 - Study habit
 - Locality
 - Viewing educational T.V. programme

Educational Implications and Recommendations:

- The main findings of the study stated that perception on student support services have the above average level among the B.Ed. students in distance education mode.
- Distance education institutions can suggest to provide more number of assignments to the students on the basis of current events to develop newspaper reading among the B.Ed. students.
- The distance education institutions may conduct special programmes like special lectures, group discussion, multi-media package for benefit of the English medium students of the B.Ed. course.
- The universities may be strengthen an online administration for the B.Ed. students in distance education mode to share the information on contact programmes, subject assignment, course material and details of examination and other particulars.

The distance education is having more scope in present and also future. The distance education mode attracts more number of people who wants to pursue higher education along with their career and also career mobility.

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